

Research Article

Development And Validation Of Five Uv – Spectrophotometric Methods For Simultaneous Estimation Of Ramipril And Amlodipine Besylate In Capsules

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ABSTRACT

Ramipril (RAMP) and Amlodipine Besylate (AMLO) in combination is frequently recommended for treating hypertension and other cardiac problems. This combination is available in diverse dosage forms like tablets, capsules. The current work was focused on establishing and validating simple and reproducible Five UV –Spectrophotometric methods for simultaneous determination of Ramipril (RAMP) and Amlodipine besylate (AMLO) in bulk and capsules. The proposed UV Spectrophotometric methods gave an opportunity to analyze a combination in multiple ways. Method A is absorption correction method, where RAMP and AMLO were determined at 208 nm and 360 nm. Method B is area under curve correction method, where RAMP and AMLO were determined at 207-217 nm and 327-385 nm. Method C is spectrum subtraction method where RAMP and AMLO were determined at 208 nm and 237 nm. Method D is ratio difference method where RAMP and AMLO were determined at 220-230 nm and 230-240 nm, respectively. Method E is first derivative coupled three wavelength method where AMLO was determined at 332 nm and the difference between absorbance at 265 nm and 275 nm (Difference is zero for AMLO) is used for the determination of RAMP. The linearity of proposed methods was investigated in range of 2-10 μ g/ml, 4-20 μ g/ml for RAMP and AMLO. The proposed all methods were validated according to ICH guidelines and results were found to be accurate, reproducible and consistent. It was successfully applied for the analysis of these drugs in marketed formulation and could be effectively used for the routine analysis of formulation containing anyone of the above drugs or a combination.

INTRODUCTION

Now-a-days, changes in food habits, lifestyle, and increase in stress have a large impact on escalation

of number of hypertension cases. According to the global health observatory data released by WHO, the number of people with uncontrolled

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hypertension rose from 600 million in 1980 to 1 billion in 2008 [1]. As, the people with hypertension advances, the need and market for antihypertensives gets immensely high. Hence, many therapies using different classes of hypertensives based on patient and their health situation has been developed. Among different combination therapies, combining calcium channel blockers with ACE Inhibitors was one of the popular way of therapy [2] as, both calcium channel blockers and ACE inhibitors help in dilation of blood vessels and reduce cardiac output and even can address cardiac complications along with hypertension. Some examples of such combination were Trandolapril and Verapamil, Amlodipine and Benazepril, Ramipril and Amlodipine, Enalapril and Felodipine, Amlodipine and Perindopril [3].

In present work, combination of ramipril and amlodipine besylate capsules was selected. Ramipril is a ACE inhibitor with IUPAC name (2S,3aS,6aS)-1-[(2S)-2-[(2S)-1-ethoxy-1-oxo-4-phenylbutan-2-yl]amino}propanoyl]octahydrocyclopenta[b]pyrrole-2-carboxylic acid [Fig.1] which is widely used in high blood pressure and congestive heart failure by inhibiting conversion of Angiotensin I to Angiotensin II [4-6]. On the other hand, Amlodipine Besylate is a calcium channel blocker with IUPAC name 3-ethyl 5-methyl 2-[(2-aminoethoxy)methyl]-4-(2-chlorophenyl)-6-methyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate [Fig.2] inhibits the movement of calcium ions into vascular smooth muscle cells and cardiac muscle cells thus ,alleviating the increased cardiac output [7-9]. By reviewing literature it was observed that there are many methods reported to determine either RAMP [10-13] or AMLO [14-18] alone or in combination [19-23]. But to the best of our knowledge, none has been reported for simultaneous estimation of RAMP and AMLO in their capsule dosage form by UV –Spectrophotometric methods. So, main

aim of the present work is to develop and validate five different UV –Spectrophotometric methods for Simultaneous estimation of RAMP and AMLO in capsule dosage form.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

Working standards (API) of RAMP and AMLO were kindly gifted by MSN Labs, Hyderabad. RAMP and AMLO were used as working standard without further purification. Based on several solubility trails with different solvents it was found that both RAMP and AMLO were soluble in Methanol. So methanol was selected as solvent for analysis. Methanol was supplied by Merck Pvt Ltd, Mumbai. STAMACE Capsules (each capsule contains contain Ramipril IP 2.5 mg and Amlodipine Besylate 5 mg) were obtained from local pharmacy.

2.2. Preparation of Standard solutions of RAMP and AMLO:

Individual standard primary stock solutions of RAMP (1000 μ g/ml) and AMLO (1000 μ g/ml) were prepared by dissolving 50 mg of RAMP and 50 mg of AMLO in 50 ml of methanol. RAMP and AMLO working standard solution 100 μ g/ml was prepared by transferring 2.5 ml from primary stock solution to a 25 ml volumetric flask and dilute up to 25 ml with methanol respectively. Appropriate and accurate volume aliquots of stock solutions were transferred to 10 ml calibrated flasks and made up to volume with methanol to give concentrations from 2-10 μ g/ml for RAMP and 4-20 μ g/ml for AMLO.

2.3. Methods

2.3.1. Method A. Absorption correction method (ACM) [24-26]

This method describes the analysis of a binary mixture where the two components X (RAMP) and Y (AMLO) have overlapped spectra. Y shows interference at λ_{max} of X, λ_1 (208 nm), while X shows no interference with Y at another wavelength λ_2 (360 nm). The average value of

absorption factor of component Y (Abs at λ_1/Abs at λ_2) is calculated. Since the absorbance of the mixture (X+Y) at λ_2 equal to that of pure Y due to lack of contribution of X at this wavelength, so the absorption of X at λ_1 could be calculated using the following equation [Eq.1].

2.3.2. Method B: Area under curve correction method (AUC-CM) [24, 27]

This method provides a simple way to determine the concentration of the component of interest depending on the area of its absorption spectrum. For a binary mixture where the two components X and Y have partially overlapped spectra. At the region of λ_1 - λ_2 (207-217 nm), while X shows no interference with Y at another region λ_3 - λ_4 (327-385 nm); Y can be determined directly through the AUC in (λ_3 - λ_4) due to lack of contribution of X at this region, while the AUC of X at (λ_1 - λ_2) can be calculated under area under curve (AUC) factor as equation. [Eq.2.]

2.6. Method C: Spectrum subtraction method: [24]

Simple, specific, accurate and precise spectrophotometric method using spectrum subtraction was developed for simultaneous determination of RAMP and AMLO from their binary mixture. In this spectrophotometric method spectra of AMLO 12 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and RAMP 6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ were subtracted from formulation individually to obtain pure RAMP 6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and AMLO 12 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ spectra. Measure the absorbances at 208nm for RAMP and at 237nm for AMLO in obtained pure spectra and substitute the values in their respective regression equation.

2.7. Method D: Ratio difference method: [28-29]

Simple, specific, accurate and precise spectrophotometric method using ratio difference was developed for simultaneous determination of RAMP and AMLO from their binary mixture. In this spectrophotometric method upon division of a spectrum with a common divisor of other drug

absorption spectrum results in a new spectrum called ratio spectrum. Compound X (RAMP) in binary mixture can be determined from a calibration curve that relates the difference in amplitudes in ratio spectrum at λ_1 (220nm) and λ_2 (230nm) using a certain concentration of Y (4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of AMLO) as a divisor to corresponding concentration of X. Similarly compound Y (AMLO) can be obtained by using certain concentration of X (2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of RAMP) as divisor with difference between λ_3 (230nm) and λ_4 (240nm).

2.8. Method E: First derivative coupled with three wavelength method [30]

Simple, specific, accurate and precise spectrophotometric method using simultaneous equation was developed for simultaneous determination of RAMP and AMLO from their binary mixture. In this spectrophotometric method, all spectra were derivatized using first order, delta lambda 16000 and scaling factor 10. Y drug (AMLO) was measured at λ_3 (332 nm) where the RAMP has zero absorbance. In order to determine X drug two wavelengths were selected on X drug (RAMP) whose difference is zero on Y drug but have absorbance on X i.e. λ_1 (229nm) and λ_2 (237nm). In binary mixture measure the amplitudes at selected wavelengths and substitute in regression equation.

Laboratory prepared mixtures and pharmaceutical formulations were successfully analyzed using the developed methods.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

All the validation parameters were performed below were based on ICH guidelines [31].

3.1. Linearity

The proposed method showed good linearity for RAMP in the concentration range of 2-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and AMLO 4-20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Overlay spectra [Fig.3-8] and Calibration graphs [Fig 9-18] of RAMP and AMLO for five methods were listed in figures. R2

values for five methods were tabulated in summary table [Table.1].

3.2. Precision

Inter-day and intra-day precision for simultaneous equation method were calculated in terms of %RSD. The experiment was repeated 3 times in a day for intra-day and on 3 different days for inter-day precision. The values confirmed the precision of the method were given in the summary table [Table.1].

3.3. Accuracy

Accuracy of the method was confirmed by recovery study form marketed formulation at three levels of concentration i.e. 50%, 100%, and 150% of label claim by standard addition technique. Recovery was found to be greater than 95% justified the accuracy of the method. The values were given in the summary table [Table.1].

3.4. LOD and LOQ

Calibration study was repeated for 5 times and standard deviation (SD) of the intercepts was calculated. Then LOD and LOQ were measured as follows:

$LOD = 3.3 * SD / \text{slope of calibration curve}$

$LOQ = 10 * SD / \text{slope of calibration curve}$

SD= standard deviation of intercepts

The values of LOD and LOQ are given in the summary table [Table.1].

3.5. Assay:

3.6. Preparation of Sample Solution

Weighed 10 capsules of STAMACE (Amlodipine Besylate 5 mg: Ramipril 2.5 mg) and take the powder. Then amount of powder equivalent to 5 mg was taken from drug powder and transfer into 5 ml volumetric flask later, add 2 ml of methanol, sonicated for 5 min and filtered through 0.45 micron membrane filter and make up with methanol this gives primary stock of 1000 µg/ml. Secondary stock solution 100 µg/ml for both drugs were prepared by pipetting out 1 ml from each primary stock and made them up to 10 ml with methanol.

Later prepared concentration 4 µg/ml from above stock solution by pipetting out appropriate aliquot. Applicability of the proposed method was tested by analyzing the commercially available formulation STAMACE. The results are tabulated in the summary table [Table.1].

4. CONCLUSION

In present work Five UV –Spectrophotometric methods were developed and validated for simultaneous analysis of Ramipril and Amlodipine Besylate in their combined capsule dosage form. The developed UV-Spectrophotometric methods were found to be accurate, precise. All the methods were validated as per the ICH guidelines and can be used for regular analysis of Ramipril and Amlodipine Besylate in Quality Control Laboratories

DECLARATION OF INTEREST

The authors report no conflicts of interest. The authors alone are responsible for the content and writing of this article

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EQUATION, FIGURE AND TABLE LEGENDS

Eq.1. Equation of Method A [Absorption correction method] (ACM)

Eq.2. Equation of Method B [Area under curve correction method] (AUC-CM)

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of Ramipril

Fig. 2. Chemical Structure of Amlodipine Besylate

Fig.3. Overlay spectra of RAMP and AMLO for Absorption correction method (Method –A)

Fig.4. Zero order absorption spectra of Area under curve Correction Method for RAMP (Method-B)

Fig.5. Zero order absorption spectra of Area under curve Correction Method for AMLO (Method-B)

Fig.6. Zero order absorption overlay spectra of AMLO and RAMP for Spectrum Subtraction method (Method-C)

Fig.7. Overlay ratio first derivative spectra of AMLO and RAMP for Ratio difference method (Method-D)

Fig.8. First order derivative overlay spectra of AMLO and RAMP for derivative coupled with three wavelength method (Method-E)

Fig.9. Calibration graph of RAMP for Absorption correction method (Method –A)

Fig.10. Calibration graph of AMLO for Absorption correction method (Method –A)

Fig.11. Calibration graph of RAMP for Area under curve Correction Method (Method-B)

Fig.12. Calibration graph of AMLO for Area under curve Correction Method (Method-B)

Fig.13. Calibration graph of RAMP for Spectrum subtraction Method (Method-C)

Fig.14. Calibration graph of AMLO for Spectrum subtraction Method (Method-C)

Fig.15. Calibration graph of RAMP for Ratio difference Method (Method-D)

Fig.16. Calibration graph of AMLO for Ratio difference Method (Method-D)

Fig.17. Calibration graph of RAMP for derivative coupled with three wavelength method (Method-E)

Fig.18. Calibration graph of AMLO for derivative coupled with three wavelength method (Method-E)

Table 1 Validation table of proposed methods for Simultaneous Estimation of RAMP and AMLO.

Equations:

Eq.1. Equation of Method A [Absorption correction method] (ACM)

$$\text{Abs of X at } \lambda_1 = \text{Abs } \lambda_1 (\text{X+Y}) - \text{abs1/abs2} \times \text{Abs } \lambda_2 (\text{X+Y})$$

Where; abs1/abs2 is absorption factor of pure Y (Abs at λ_1 /Abs at λ_2), Abs λ_1 and Abs λ_2 are the absorbance of the mixture of (X+Y) at λ_1 and λ_2 , respectively. The concentrations of X and Y will be calculated from the corresponding regression equation obtained by plotting the absorption values of the zero order spectra, at λ_1 and λ_2 , against their concentrations, respectively.

Eq.2. Equation of Method B [Area under curve correction method] (AUC-CM)

$$\text{AUC of X at } (\lambda_1-\lambda_2) = \text{AUC at } (\lambda_1-\lambda_2) \text{ of X+Y} - \text{AUC(1-2)/AUC(3-4)} \times \text{AUC at } (\lambda_3-\lambda_4) \text{ of X+Y}$$

Where;

AUC (1-2)/AUC (3-4) is AUC factor of pure Y [AUC at ($\lambda_1-\lambda_2$)/AUC at ($\lambda_3-\lambda_4$)], AUC at ($\lambda_3-\lambda_4$) of X+Y = AUC at ($\lambda_3-\lambda_4$) of Y only.

Figures:

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of Ramipril

Fig. 2. Chemical Structure of Amlodipine Besylate

Fig.3. Overlay spectra of RAMP and AMLO for Absorption correction method (Method –A)

Fig.4. Zero order absorption spectra of Area under curve Correction Method for RAMP (Method-B)

Fig.5. Zero order absorption spectra of Area under curve Correction Method for AMLO (Method-B)

Fig.6. Zero order absorption overlay spectra of AMLO and RAMP for Spectrum Subtraction method (Method-C)

Fig.7. Overlay ratio first derivative spectra of AMLO and RAMP for Ratio difference method (Method-D)

Fig.8. First order derivative overlay spectra of AMLO and RAMP for derivative coupled with three wavelength method (Method-E)

Fig.9. Calibration graph of RAMP for Absorption correction method (Method –A)

Fig.10. Calibration graph of AMLO for Absorption correction method (Method –A)

Fig.11. Calibration graph of RAMP for Area under curve Correction Method (Method-B)

Fig.12. Calibration graph of AMLO for Area under curve Correction Method (Method-B)

Fig.13. Calibration graph of RAMP for Spectrum subtraction Method (Method-C)

Fig.14. Calibration graph of AMLO for Spectrum subtraction Method (Method-C)

Fig.15. Calibration graph of RAMP for Ratio difference Method (Method-D)

Fig.16. Calibration graph of AMLO for Ratio difference Method (Method-D)

Fig.17. Calibration graph of RAMP for derivative coupled with three wavelength method (Method-E)

Fig.18. Calibration graph of AMLO for derivative coupled with three wavelength method (Method-E)

Tables:

Table 1 Validation table of proposed methods for Simultaneous Estimation of RAMP and AMLO.

PARAMETER		RAMP	AMLO
METHOD-A: ABSORPTION CORRECTION METHOD			
LINEARITY	Correlation coefficient (R²)	1	0.9996
	Slope	0.0374	0.0127
	Intercept	0.0855	0.0018
PRECISION	Interday	1.544	1.009
	Intraday	1.536	0.87
ACCURACY	50 %	107.3	98.4
	100%	109.9	100.3
	150%	109.3	103.9
ASSAY		100	108
LOD		0.693	0.213
LOQ		2.341	1.848
METHOD-B: AREA UNDER CURVE CORRECTION METHOD			
LINEARITY	Correlation coefficient (R²)	0.9995	0.9999
	Slope	0.0248	0.2296
	Intercept	0.0210	0.0020
PRECISION	Interday	1.544	1.039
	Intraday	1.116	0.456
ACCURACY	50 %	108.8	109.4
	100%	101.8	108.2
	150%	105.6	106.6
ASSAY		108	105.4
LOD		1.95E-15	0.218
LOQ		0.425	4.08E-14
METHOD-C: SPECTRUM SUBTRACTION METHOD			
LINEARITY	Correlation coefficient (R²)	0.9997	0.9995
	Slope	0.0372	0.0363
	Intercept	0.0883	0.0140
PRECISION	Interday	1.54	0.9
	Intraday	1.536	0.82
ACCURACY	50 %	105.4	101
	100%	108.6	106.4
	150%	108.4	108.5
ASSAY		105.3	98.4
LOD		0.696	0.42
LOQ		1.8	2.35
RATIO DIFFERENCE METHOD			
LINEARITY	Correlation coefficient (R²)	0.9999	0.9993
	Slope	0.0893	0.5548
	Intercept	0.1074	0.1288
PRECISION	Interday	1.46	1.18
	Intraday	1.425	1.64
ACCURACY	50 %	111.4	115
	100%	115.5	113.3

	150%	114.8	114.0
ASSAY		94	108.3
LOD		0.312	0.291
LOQ		1.88	3.31
FIRST DERIVATIVE COUPLED WITH THREE WAVELENGTH METHOD			
LINEARITY	Correlation coefficient (R²)	0.9992	0.9999
	Slope	0.0066	0.0027
	Intercept	0.0039	0.0010
PRECISION	Interday	1.863	1.368
	Intraday	1.722	1.489
ACCURACY	50 %	96.4	104.9
	100%	98.8	97.2
	150%	97.2	107.4
ASSAY		102.7	101.8
LOD		1.423	1.771
LOQ		1.923	3.904

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